

A STUDY ON QUALITY OF WORK LIFE AND JOB PERFORMANCE OF CONSTRUCTION WORKERS IN CHENNAI

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Abstract:

The better Quality of Work Life (QWL) is important for any industrial organizations to continue to absorb and hold workers. QWL is an inclusive programme designed to increase job performance of workers, improving learning process in workplace and facilitates workers to have better development and transition. The compensation, working conditions, development and social integration are the important quality of work life dimensions for construction workers. The results indicate that there is significant difference between socio-economic status of workers and quality of work life dimensions for construction workers. Besides, compensation, working condition, social integration and development are positively and significantly influencing job performance of construction workers. To improve the job performance of construction workers, they must be provided with better salary and safe and healthy working environment. The opportunities should be provide to them for their personal development and team work and social relationship among them must be encouraged.

Key Words: Construction Workers, Job Performance, Quality of Work Life

1. Introduction:

Now-a-days, Quality of Work Life (QWL) is one of the most significant matters in almost all industries. No industrial sector is becoming successful with modern technologies only because for the adoption of technologies also, industrial sector needs to have quality workers Quality of Work Life is the idea that is begun in the late 1960s. From that time till now the concept is getting higher level of importance every industrial sector, at every work environment.

Primarily quality of work life is concentrating on the impacts of employment on healthiness and welfare of the workers. But at present its objectives have been altered. Every industry wants to give better working environment to their workers including all non financial and financial benefits, thus, they can keep their employees for the longer period and for the attainment of the objective of industrial organizations. The quality of work life believes workers as an advantage to the industrial organization rather than disadvantages. It considers that workers perform their jobs better when they are permitted to contribute in managing and involving in decision making process in their work.

The better Quality of Work Life (QWL) is important for any industrial organizations to continue to absorb and hold workers. QWL is an inclusive programme designed to increase job performance of workers, improving learning process in workplace and facilitates workers to have better development and transition (Walton, 2005). The rapidly growing construction industry provides employment opportunities for large number workers, at the same time, the construction workers are highly oppressed especially in cities. Therefore, it is necessary to study quality of work life and job performance of construction workers in Chennai city.

2. Methodology:

The present study is carried out in Chennai city. The construction workers are chosen by using random sampling method. The data are collected from 200 construction workers through pre-tested and structured questionnaire. To study the socio-economic status of construction workers, the percentage analysis is carried out. The mean and standard deviation are calculated for quality of work life dimensions for construction workers. To study the difference between socio-economic status of workers and quality of work life dimensions for construction workers, the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test is used. To analyze the influence of quality of work life dimensions for construction workers on their job performance, the multiple linear regression is done.

3. Results and Discussion:

3.1 Socio-Economic Status of Construction Workers:

The socio-economic status of construction workers was analyzed and the results are presented in Table-1. The results show that 65.50 per cent of workers are males and the remaining 34.50 per cent of workers are females. It is clear that 44.00 per cent of workers are in the age group of 31 - 40 years followed by 21 - 30 years (29.50 per cent), 41 - 50 years (18.00 per cent) above 50 years (8.50 per cent).

The results indicate that 48.50 per cent of workers are illiterates followed by secondary education (32.00 per cent) and higher secondary education (19.50 per cent). It is observed that 43.50 per cent of workers have work experience of 6 - 10 years followed by 1 - 5 years (30.50 per cent) and more than 10 years (26.00 per cent). The results reveal that 50.50 per cent of workers are in the monthly income of Rs.10,001- Rs.15,000 followed by less than Rs.10,000 (28.00 per cent) and more than Rs.15,000 (21.50 per cent).

Table 1: Socio-Economic Status of Construction Workers

Socio-Economic Status	Number of Workers	Percentage
Gender		
Male	131	65.50
Female	69	34.50
Age Group		
21 - 30 years	59	29.50
31 - 40 years	88	44.00
41 - 50 years	36	18.00
Above 50 years	17	8.50
Educational Qualification		
Illiterate	97	48.50
Secondary	64	32.00
Higher Secondary	39	19.50
Work Experience		
1 - 5 years	61	30.50
6 - 10 years	87	43.50
More than 10 years	52	26.00
Monthly Income		
Less than Rs.10,000	56	28.00
Rs.10,001- Rs.15,000	101	50.50
More than Rs.15,000	43	21.50

3.2 Quality of Work Life Dimensions for Construction Workers:

The quality of work life dimensions for construction workers was analyzed and the results are given as below.

3.2.1 Compensation Dimension:

The compensation dimension for construction workers was analyzed and the results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Compensation Dimension for Construction Workers

Compensation	Mean	Standard Deviation
I receive enough wage	3.32	1.16
I like to continue in the present work irrespective of wage	3.61	1.10
I am under paid in my work	3.68	1.15
I have fair chances for increment of wage	3.62	1.11
Wage in this work is as good as most other works	3.38	1.14

The results show that the construction workers are agreed with they like to continue in the present work irrespective of wage, they are under paid in their work and they have fair chances for increment of wage, while, they are neutral with they receive enough wage and wage in this work is as good as most other works.

3.2.2 Working Condition Dimension:

The working condition dimension for construction workers was analyzed and the results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Working Condition Dimension for Construction Workers

Working Condition	Mean	Standard Deviation
My work place has a favourable work environment	3.65	1.07
The working environment in my work place is encouraging	3.41	1.14
The work environment puts emphasis on safety of workers	3.39	1.09
It is easier to receive materials for efficient work	3.66	1.10
Workers are given adequate facilities in work place	3.43	1.02

The results indicate that the construction workers are agreed with their work place has a favourable work environment and it is easier to receive materials for efficient work, while, they are neutral with the working environment in their work place is encouraging, the work environment puts emphasis on safety of workers and workers are given adequate facilities in work place.

3.2.3 Development Dimension:

The development dimension for construction workers was analyzed and the results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Development Dimension for Construction Workers

Development	Mean	Standard Deviation
Work carried in advanced ways are recognized	3.67	1.04
Changes are given to learn new methods	3.63	1.07
The work facilitates development of workers	3.70	1.16
The work helps the personal improvement of workers	3.69	1.19
It gives job security	3.33	1.20

The results reveal that the construction workers are agreed with work carried in advanced ways are recognized, changes are given to learn new methods, the work facilitates development of workers and the work helps the personal improvement of workers, while, they are neutral with it gives job security.

3.2.4 Social Integration Dimension:

The social integration dimension for construction workers was analyzed and the results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Social Integration Dimension for Construction Workers

Social Integration	Mean	Standard Deviation
We have the sense of one community	3.72	1.07
We have no problem in team work	3.64	1.05
We share our feelings and ideas	3.71	1.12
We are mutually helpful	3.73	1.13
We share our workloads	3.61	1.06

The results imply that the construction workers are agreed with they have the sense of one community, they have no problem in team work, they share their feelings and ideas and they are mutually helpful and they share their workloads.

3.3 Socio-Economic Status of Workers and Quality of Work Life Dimensions for Construction Workers:

The difference between socio-economic status of workers and quality of work life dimensions for construction workers was studied by using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test and the results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Difference between Socio-Economic Status of Workers and Quality of Work Life Dimensions for Construction Workers

Particulars	F-Value	Sig.
Gender and Quality of Work Life Dimensions for Construction Workers	17.842**	.000
Age Group and Quality of Work Life Dimensions for Construction Workers	14.950**	.000
Educational Qualification and Quality of Work Life Dimensions for Construction Workers	19.364**	.000
Work Experience and Quality of Work Life Dimensions for Construction Workers	16.178**	.000
Monthly Income and Quality of Work Life Dimensions for Construction Workers	18.690**	.000

**Significant at one per cent level.

The results show that the F-values are significant at one per cent level revealing that there is significant difference between socio-economic status of workers and quality of work life dimensions for construction workers. Hence, the null hypothesis of there is no significant difference between socio-economic status of workers and quality of work life dimensions for construction workers is rejected.

3.4 Influence of Quality of Work Life Dimensions for Construction Workers on Their Job Performance:

To analyze the influence of quality of work life dimensions for construction workers on their job performance, the multiple linear regression is done and the results are presented in Table-7. The coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) is 0.57 and adjusted R^2 is 0.55 showing that the regression model is good fit. It implies that 55.00 per cent of the variation in dependent variable is explained by the independent variables. The F-value of 17.235 is statistically significant at one per cent level revealing that the regression model is significant.

Table 7: Influence of Quality of Work Life Dimensions for Construction Workers on Their Job Performance

Quality of Work Life Dimensions	Regression Co-efficients	t-Value	Sig.
Intercept	1.102**	6.119	.000
Compensation (X_1)	.375**	5.480	.000
Working Condition (X_2)	.349**	5.106	.000
Development (X_3)	.273**	4.758	.000
Social Integration (X_4)	.291**	4.912	.000
R^2	0.57	-	-

Adjusted R ²	0.55	-	-
F	17.235	-	0.00

** Significant at one per cent level

The results reveal that compensation, working condition, social integration and development are positively and significantly influencing job performance of construction workers at one per cent level. Thus, the null hypothesis of there is no significant influence of quality of work life dimensions for construction workers on their job performance is rejected.

4. Conclusion:

The foregoing analysis indicates that compensation, working conditions, development and social integration are the important quality of work life dimensions for construction workers. The results show that there is significant difference between socio-economic status of workers and quality of work life dimensions for construction workers. Meanwhile, compensation, working condition, social integration and development are positively and significantly influencing job performance of construction workers. To improve the job performance of construction workers, they must be provided with better salary and safe and healthy working environment. The opportunities should be provide to them for their personal development and team work and social relationship among them must be encouraged.

5. References:

1. Archana Chandra, Pradhyuman Singh Lakhawat and Poonam Vishwakarma, "Study on Measuring the Quality of Work Life among Third Grade Employees in Naini Industrial Area", International Journal of Technological Exploration and Learning, 2013, 2(6): pp.318-321.
2. Brian Ballou and Norman H. Godwin, "Quality of Work Life", Strategic Finance, 2007, 89(4): pp.40-45.
3. Considine, G. and R. Callus, "The Quality of Work Life of Australian Employees - The Development of an Index", Working Paper 73, 2003, ACIRRT, University of Sydney, Sydney.
4. David Lewis, Kevin Brazil, Paul Krueger, Lynne Lohfeld, Erin Tjam, "Extrinsic and Intrinsic Determinants of Quality of Work Life", International Journal of Health Care Quality Assurance, 2001, 14(3), pp.9-15.
5. Elizur, Dov., "Quality Circles and Quality of Work Life", International Journal of Manpower, 1990, 11(6): pp.3-5.
6. Gayathiri, R. and Lalitha Ramakrishnan, "Quality of Work Life – Linkage with Job Satisfaction and Performance", International Journal of Business and Management Invention, 2(1): pp.1-8.
7. Hoque, M. E. and Rahman, A., "Quality of Working Life and Job Behaviour of Workers in Bangladesh: A Comparative Study of Private and Public Sectors", Indian Journal of Industrial Relations, 1997, 35(2): pp.175-184.
8. Juuti, Pauli, "Work in the 1990s: Improving Productivity and the Quality of Working Life", Industrial and Commercial Training, 1991, 23(1): p.6.
9. Ka Wai Chan and Thomas A Wyatt, "Quality of Work Life: A Study of Employees in Shanghai, China", Asia Pacific Business Review, 2007, 13(4): pp.501-516.
10. Mirvis, P. H., and Lawler, E. E., "Accounting for the Quality of Work Life", Journal of Occupational Behaviour, 1984, 5: pp.197-212.
11. Nasal Saraji, G, and Dargahi, H., (2006) "Study of Quality of Work Life (QWL)", Iranian Journal of Public Health, 2005, 35(4): pp.8-14.
12. Raduan Che Rose, Loo See Beh, Jegak Uli and Khairuddin Idris, "Quality of Work Life: Implications o Career Dimensions", University of Malaya, 2005, Malaysia.
13. Sarang Shanker Bhola, "A Study of Quality of Working Life in Casting and Machine Shop Industry in Kolhapur", Finance India, 2006, 20(1): pp.202-208.
14. Stephen, A. and Dhanapal, D., "Quality of Work Life in Small Scale Industrial Units: Employers and Employees Perspectives", European Journal of Social Sciences, 2012, 28(2): pp.260-270.
15. Tarek Hassan Abdeen, "Company Performance: Does Quality of Work Life Really Matter?", Management Research News, 2002, 25(8 / 9 / 10): pp.8-11.
16. Walton, R.E., "Quality of Work Life (QWL) Measurement", <http://www.Syn.Com/QWL.htm>, 2005, pp.1-3.
17. Wilcock, Anne, Wright, Marina, "Quality of Work Life in the Knitwear Sector of the Canadian Textile Industry", Public Personnel Management, 1991, 20(4): pp.457-459.
18. B. Shanmugam & Dr. R. Ganapathi, "A Study on Factors Affecting Quality of Work Life of Employees in Automobile Industrial Units", International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 158-162, 2017.